

EFFECT OF ORGANIC SPRAY ON QUALITY AND ECONOMICS OF TOMATO (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) cv. GT 2 UNDER SOUTH GUJARAT CONDITION

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Abstract

The experiment entitled “Effect of organic spray on quality and economics of tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) cv. GT 2 under south Gujarat condition” was carried out during rabi season 2017-18 at the Regional Horticultural Research Station, ASPEE College of Horticulture and Forestry, Navsari Agricultural University, Navsari, Gujarat. The experiment was conducted with a set of twelve treatments viz., T₁ (Control or No spray), T₂ (Water spray at 25 DATP), T₃ (Water spray at 25 & 50 DATP), T₄ (Novel spray 2 % at 25 DATP), T₅ (Novel spray 1 % at 25 & 50 DATP), T₆ (Vermiwash 3 % at 25 DATP), T₇ (Vermiwash 1.5 % at 25 & 50 DATP), T₈ (Panchagavya 3 % at 25 DATP), T₉ (Panchagavya 1.5 % at 25 & 50 DATP), T₁₀ (Moringa extract 3 % at 25 DATP), T₁₁ (Moringa extract 1.5 % at 25 & 50 DATP) and T₁₂ (Moringa extract 1 % at 25, 50 & 75 DATP). The experiment was conducted in a Randomized Blocked Design (RBD) with three replications. The results revealed that among different treatments, panchagavya @ 3 % at 25 DATP was increase more or less TSS, acidity, shelf life and economics of tomato. While, foliar spray of Novel 2 % at 25 DATP received higher lycopene content.

Key words: Panchagavya, Vermiwash, Moringa extract, Novel.

Introduction

Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) is one of the most important vegetable crop grown all over the world. It is self-pollinated and a member of solanaceae family having chromosome number 2n = 24. Foliar application of organic spray has been widely used as supplemental dose of major and minor nutrients, plant hormones, stimulants and other beneficial substances. Plant hormones can be used to increase yield per unit area because they influence every phase of plant growth and development. There are five groups of growth regulators among them, cytokinin enhances food production. Zeatin is one of the most common forms of naturally occurring cytokinin in plants. Banana Pseudo stem sap contain huge amount of macro and micro nutrients which act as growth booster solution. Vermiwash contains N, P, K, Ca and hormones such as auxins, cytokinins and many useful microbes like heterotrophic bacteria, fungi etc. When applied on the crops, it removes the imbalances in terms of physical, chemical and physiological aspects and harmonizes the basic element, which revitalizes the growth process. Plant sprayed with panchagavya invariable produce bigger leaves with dense canopy. It is also increases the sugar content and aroma of fruits as well as crops to induce early flowering. Moringa Leaf Extract application improves crops performance, resulting from vigorous seedling growth, maintained optimum tissue water status, improve membranes stability, enhance antioxidant levels and activate plant defense system, increase levels of plant secondary metabolites and reduce uptake of undesirable Na⁺ and Cl⁻.

Materials and methods

The field experiment with entitled, “Effect of organic spray on quality and economics of tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) cv. GT 2 under south Gujarat condition” was conducted during rabi season of 2017-18 at the Regional Horticultural Research Station, ASPEE College of Horticulture and Forestry, Navsari Agricultural University, Navsari, Gujarat. The experiment was laid out in Randomized Blocked Design with three replication and twelve treatments viz., T₁ (Control or No spray), T₂ (Water spray at 25 DATP), T₃ (Water spray at 25 & 50 DATP), T₄ (Novel spray 2 % at 25 DATP), T₅ (Novel spray 1 % at 25 & 50

DATP), T₆ (Vermiwash 3 % at 25 DATP), T₇ (Vermiwash 1.5 % at 25 & 50 DATP), T₈ (Panchagavya 3 % at 25 DATP), T₉ (Panchagavya 1.5 % at 25 & 50 DATP), T₁₀ (Moringa extract 3 % at 25 DATP), T₁₁ (Moringa extract 1.5 % at 25 & 50 DATP) and T₁₂ (Moringa extract 1 % at 25, 50 & 75 DATP). The gross plot and net plot size of experiment was 4.5 m × 3.6 m and 2.7 m × 2.7 m, respectively. The spacing of tomato plants was 90 × 45 cm. All solution was collected and considered as 100 % concentration and same was used for preparing the require solution.

The five fruits collected from the selected plant at the fourth harvest and same fruits were used to find out the TSS of fruits of the respective treatment with the help of digital Erma hand refractometer at room temperature. The method described by Ranganna (1986) was adopted for estimation of titrable acidity. The spectrophotometric method for lycopene estimation as described by Ranganna (1986) was adopted. The five mature fruits of fourth harvest from each net plot of the treatment were taken and kept under ambient conditions in the well ventilated room till they remained firm and having marketability on the base of visual observation. The period in days was noted for each fruit of the sample and average days was calculated as shelf life of fruits of the respective treatment and presented in days.

The gross realization in term of rupees per hectare was calculated on the basis of the total yield of tomato for each treatment using the prevailing market prices of produce. The cost of cultivation of the crop for each treatment was worked out by taking into consideration the cost of all the inputs used and operations followed starting from the preparatory tillage to harvesting. The net realization was worked out by deducting the total cost of cultivation from gross realization per hectare for each treatment and recorded accordingly.

The benefit cost ratio (BCR) was calculated as follows:

$$\text{BCR} = \frac{\text{Net realization}}{\text{Total cost of cultivation}}$$

Table-1 : Effect of organic spray on quality parameters of tomato cv. GT 2 under south Gujarat condition.

Treatments	TSS (°Brix)	Acidity (%)	Lycopene content (mg 100g ⁻¹)	Shelf life (days)
T ₁ : Control (No spray)	3.98	0.47	3.56	5.33
T ₂ : Water spray (25 DATP)	4.01	0.47	3.56	5.67

T ₃	: Water spray (25 & 50 DATP)	4.04	0.48	3.67	6.33
T ₄	: Novel spray (2 % at 25 DATP)	4.45	0.52	4.29	7.33
T ₅	: Novel spray (1 % 25 & 50 DATP)	4.39	0.50	3.95	7.67
T ₆	: Vermiwash (3 % at 25 DATP)	4.41	0.53	4.00	7.67
T ₇	: Vermiwash spray (1.5 % at 25 & 50 DATP)	4.37	0.51	3.80	7.33
T ₈	: <i>Panchagavya</i> (3 % at 25 DATP)	4.46	0.54	4.20	7.67
T ₉	: <i>Panchagavya</i> (1.5 % at 25 & 50 DATP)	4.40	0.54	4.15	7.33
T ₁₀	: Moringa extract (3% at 25 DATP)	4.07	0.50	3.61	6.00
T ₁₁	: Moringa extract (1.5 % at 25 & 50 DATP)	4.16	0.50	3.73	7.00
T ₁₂	: Moringa extract (1% at 25, 50 & 75 DATP)	4.12	0.51	3.74	6.33
S. Em.±		0.12	0.015	0.17	0.36
C.D. at 5%		0.36	0.044	0.48	1.06
C.V. %		5.03	5.18	7.42	9.19

Table-2 : Effect of organic spray on economics of tomato cv. GT 2 under south Gujarat condition.

Treatments	Gross return (Rs.)	Net return (Rs.)	BCR
T ₁ : Control (No spray)	219910	127913	1.39
T ₂ : Water spray (25 DATP)	232950	138379	1.46
T ₃ : Water spray (25 & 50 DATP)	243150	146373	1.51
T ₄ : Novel spray (2 % at 25 DATP)	290340	184637	1.75
T ₅ : Novel spray (1 % 25 & 50 DATP)	289460	183386	1.73
T ₆ : Vermiwash (3 % at 25 DATP)	297520	190186	1.77
T ₇ : Vermiwash spray (1.5 % at 25 & 50 DATP)	264470	160871	1.55
T ₈ : <i>Panchagavya</i> (3 % at 25 DATP)	332370	217546	1.89
T ₉ : <i>Panchagavya</i> (1.5 % at 25 & 50 DATP)	316520	203022	1.79
T ₁₀ : Moringa extract (3% at 25 DATP)	249750	147570	1.44
T ₁₁ : Moringa extract (1.5 % at 25 & 50 DATP)	261980	157467	1.51
T ₁₂ : Moringa extract (1% at 25, 50 & 75 DATP)	260390	155360	1.48

Result and discussion

The results on various quality parameters are presented in **Table-1**. The quality characters of tomato fruit was significantly influenced by foliar spray of various organic sprays as compared to the no spray. Significantly maximum TSS (4.46 °Brix) was obtained with *panchagavya* 3 % at 25 DATP (T₈). In case of shelf life, treatments T₈ (*Panchagavya* 3 % at 25 DATP), T₅ (Novel spray 1 % at 25 & 50 DATP) and T₆ (Vermiwash 3 % at 25 DATP) gave significantly higher shelf life (7.67 days) of tomato fruit. Similar result was obtained by Ramesh *et al.* (2015) that the increased quality character of tomato fruit by foliar application of organic manure might be because of fermented liquid organic manure contain microbial load and plant growth promoting substances with addition to nutrient that helps in improving plant growth and metabolic activity which further could have enhanced the post harvest parameter and shelf life in tomato. Kumar *et al.* (2017) observed that the increased quality characters might be due to the translocation of sugar and growth modifying substances in snake gourd. Significantly, maximum acidity (0.54 %) was cited into T₈ and T₉. However,

significantly higher lycopene content (4.29 mg 100 g⁻¹) resulted in foliar spray of novel 2 % at 25 DATP (T₄).

The economics of various treatments under study was work out and cited in **Table-2**. The data revealed that the maximum net return, gross return and return per rupee (2,17,546 & 3,32,370 Rs ha⁻¹ and 1.89, respectively) was received with treatment *panchagavya* 3 % at 25 DATP (T₈) as compared to rest of all the treatments. The result of economics by various treatments was supported by earlier workers; Gopakkali and Sharanappa (2014) in chilli, Panchal *et al.* (2017) in chickpea.

Conclusions

From the forgoing result of the experiment, it can be concluded that the plant sprayed with *panchagavya* @ 3 % at 25 DATP more or less increase quality characters and economics of tomato cv. GT 2 under south Gujarat condition.

References

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